

The phyllosphere microbiome and its applications in sustainable agriculture

Karen Uchida¹

¹Department of Plant Sciences, University of Cambridge, UK

Summary

Plants interact with diverse microorganisms that collectively form a microbiome. These microbial communities play an important role in maintaining plant health and offer promising alternatives to synthetic fertilisers and pesticides which harm the environment. The phyllosphere refers to above-ground portion of a plant. This review provides an overview of the current research on the phyllosphere microbiome in major food crops and discusses its potential applications in agriculture. Further studies are needed to expand our knowledge of microbiome functions and link them to plant genetics. This could unlock novel microbiome-based approaches that support sustainable food production for the growing global population.

Introduction

Current agricultural practices are detrimental to the environment with the extensive use of fertilisers and pesticides disrupting the global biogeochemical cycles and leading to the loss of natural biodiversity (Campbell et al., 2017). With the global population projected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050, food demand is expected to rise by up to 60% between 2010 and 2050 (UN, 2017; van Dijk et al., 2021). Hence it is essential to shift towards sustainable agricultural practices that maximise food production while minimising environmental impacts (Garnett et al., 2013; Richardson et al., 2023). Harnessing plant-associated microbes is proposed as a promising alternative to synthetic chemicals to enable sustainable food production (Hu, Chen and He, 2022).

Plants interact with diverse microorganisms including bacteria, fungi, archaea, protists and viruses that form the plant microbiota (Berg et al., 2020; Zilber-Rosenberg & Rosenberg, 2008). The term microbiome, first introduced by Whipps and his team in 1988, describes a collection of genomes, metabolites and functions of the microbiota and their interactions with its host plant and the surrounding environment (Marchesi and Ravel, 2015). Distinct microbiomes can be found across different parts of a plant including the phyllosphere, which encompasses all above-

ground parts including leaves, stems (caulosphere), flowers (carposphere) and fruits (anthosphere) (Figure 1A, B) (Lindow and Brandl, 2003).

Leaves are among the largest microhabitats on Earth with their total surface estimated to be twice the size of all land area and inhabited by up to 10^{26} bacteria (Vorholt, 2012). They are colonised by epiphytes on the surface and endophytes within the internal tissues (Figure 1C) (Sohrabi et al., 2023). Microbial species are heterogeneously distributed across the leaf surface (Figure 1D) (Kusstascher et al., 2020; Remus-Emsermann et al., 2014; Saarenpää et al., 2024). For example, some bacterial species inhabit glandular trichomes on tomato leaves where

plant metabolites accumulate (Kusstascher et al., 2020). Despite the importance of spatial distribution for microbial interactions with plants and other microbes, it is often overlooked in studies that rely solely on bioinformatic approaches.

The phyllosphere microbiome is a complex network of plant-microbe and microbe-microbe interactions (Figure 1B) (Chaudhry et al., 2021). Within this network, microorganisms that are consistently found across samples from a specific habitat or a plant are known as the core microbiomes (Shade and Handelsman, 2012). Computational analyses of microbial networks are used to identify the “hub” or “keystone” species, which interact with multiple species and play a central role in shaping the microbiome (Agler et al., 2016). These key species are targets for manipulating the microbiome as changing their abundance can significantly alter the overall microbiome composition and structure (Toju et al., 2018).

Most plant microbiome research has focused on below-ground microbiomes which accounted for over 80% of studies in cereal crops (Michl, Berg and Cernava, 2023). Nevertheless, the phyllosphere microbiome is gaining attention for its role in promoting growth and disease resistance (De Mandal and Jeon, 2023). This review will provide an overview of the current state of phyllosphere microbiome research with a focus on agriculturally important food crops and discuss their potential applications in sustainable agriculture.

Main

Current phyllosphere microbiome research

To gain an overview of the current state of the phyllosphere microbiome research, a literature search was conducted on the Web of Science by using the keywords “Plant,” “Phyllosphere” and “Microbiome.” This resulted in 584 primary research articles and 89 reviews as of 1st March 2025. Within the research articles, entries that were miscategorised, such as reviews, book chapters or studies focused exclusively on the rhizosphere were excluded, resulting in a list of 503 publications. While phyllosphere microbiome research began in the early 2000s as evident by key reviews including Lindow and Brandl (2003) and Vorholt (2012), the earliest articles from this search was from 2013 (Figure 2A). This could be due to changes in terminology over time, highlighting the limitation of this search method. Nevertheless, the list was used for further analysis to gain an insight into the trends in phyllosphere microbiome research over the past decade.

Figure 2: Overview of current phyllosphere microbiome research. (A) Number of research articles published per year. Articles were categorised as agriculture (food crops or cash crops) or ecology (non-agricultural plant species) based on the plant species studied. (B) Diversity of food crops studied with the number of articles indicated for each crop. (C) Proportion of studies using amplicon or metagenomic sequencing. (D) Types of microorganisms studied using amplicon sequencing.

The growing interest in phyllosphere microbiome research was evident in the increasing number of publications (Figure 2A). Overall, 57.5% of the articles focused on food crops such as cereals, vegetables and fruits or cash crops including rapeseed, cacao and cotton, while 39.1% covered non-agricultural plants including wild trees, grasses and shrubs. The emphasis on agriculturally relevant crops is promising as this could drive progress towards harnessing microbiomes in agriculture.

Although the phyllosphere microbiome has been studied in over 70 different food crops, the research primarily focused on globally important staple crops such as rice, wheat and maize (Figure 2B). Tomatoes and lettuce were among the most extensively studied vegetables. Grapevines were widely researched in Europe due to their economic value for fruit and wine production (Awad et al., 2023). Highly studied crops such as rice had extensive resources, including high-quality sequencing datasets that can be used for further studies (Masuda et al., 2024; Su et al., 2022). Research focused on specific crops can help build robust model systems to advance our understanding of microbiomes and apply them to other plants.

A key step in microbiome research is using sequencing to characterise the composition, abundance, diversity, and structure of a given microbiome. Two commonly used sequencing techniques are amplicon or metagenomic sequencing (Liu et al., 2021). Amplicon sequencing involves the amplification of a variable genetic region (Regalado et al., 2020). For prokaryotes and archaea, this locus is in the 16S ribosomal RNA (rRNA), while in eukaryotes, the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of the 18S rRNA is used (Schoch et al., 2012). In contrast, metagenomic approaches use shotgun or long-read sequencing to characterise the entire genetic content of a sample, including plasmids and viruses (Handelsman et al., 1998; Masuda et al., 2024; Portik, Brown & Pierce-Ward, 2022). While some studies categorise amplicon sequencing as 'metagenomics,' it is important to distinguish these terminologies as amplification-based methods do not characterise the entire genome (Aguar-Pulido et al., 2016; Quince et al., 2017). In this review, the term 'metagenomics' specifically refers to whole-genome sequencing.

Over 80% of studies relied on amplicon sequencing (Figure 2C). Although it is high-throughput and cost-effective, major drawbacks include low taxonomic-level resolution and primer bias which can hinder the detection of certain taxa (Liu et al., 2021). Nevertheless, amplicon data are often used in correlation-based network analyses to predict microbial interactions and identify key taxa (Faust and Raes, 2012; Sapkota, Jørgensen and Nicolaisen, 2017). Metagenomics can overcome these limitations by providing species-level classification, enabling advanced functional characterisation (Su et al., 2022). Integrating sequencing with multi-omics approaches, such as transcriptomics and metabolomics can expand our understanding of microbiome functions (Wu et al., 2024). However, it is important to note that these bulk analysis methods fail to capture the spatial distribution of microbe-microbe interactions which influence

their functions (Remus-Emsermann and Schlechter, 2018). Therefore, additional experiments are needed to validate the inferred observations.

Despite being termed 'microbiome', most studies have primarily focused on bacteria and fungi, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding the diversity and functions of phyllosphere archaea, protists and viruses (Figure 2D). This is due to the widespread use of bacterial and fungal-specific amplicon sequencing and the lower abundance of archaea and protists in the phyllosphere compared to bacteria and fungi, which makes them difficult to detect (Taffner et al., 2019). Nevertheless, archaea and protists have key roles in plant nutrient cycling and pathogen control (Sun et al., 2021; Taffner et al., 2019). This underscores the need to diversify research methods to gain a more complete understanding of the microbiome.

Box 1: Hotspots of phyllosphere microbiome research

To investigate the global distribution of phyllosphere microbiome research, the study locations provided in the methods section were mapped (Figure 3). This revealed that research on food crops was concentrated in China, the United States and India. The distribution mirrored trends observed in a meta-analysis of over 300,000 plant science publications, which highlighted the geographic disparities in current research (Marks et al., 2023). The study also pointed out the bias towards studying a limited number of plant species, primarily model systems and major crops, which was also observed in phyllosphere microbiome research.

Microbial products are often proposed as promising tools for sustainable agriculture as part of achieving global goals such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal Zero Hunger (Hu, Chen and He, 2022). However, harnessing microbes would require expanding research to diverse geographic locations and plant species, including orphan crops and wild varieties of commercial crops (Cernava, 2024; Yin et al., 2023). This would facilitate the development of microbiome-based strategies tailored to different regions (Ayeni et al., 2024).

Figure 3: Geographic distribution of phyllosphere microbiome research. Green circles representing include studies on major food and cash crops.

Numerous studies have investigated the effect of biotic, abiotic and anthropogenic factors on the composition of the phyllosphere microbiome as reviewed by Bashir et al. (2022). Building on these findings, the remainder of this review will focus on their potential applications in sustainable agriculture. Three main strategies for harnessing the phyllosphere microbiome include: (1) engineering microbial communities to enhance beneficial traits, (2) manipulating host plant genetics to naturally recruit favourable microbiomes and (3) adapting agricultural practices to promote the formation of beneficial phyllosphere microbiome.

Engineering the phyllosphere microbiome

The knowledge of phyllosphere microbiome diversity and composition can be applied to design microbial communities with desired functions using microbiome engineering (Figure 4). (Lawson et al., 2019). This include bottom-up approaches where the individual microorganisms are isolated and characterised (Ke, Wang and Yoshikuni, 2021). Microbial strains with beneficial traits can be used to build synthetic communities (SynComs) or their metabolites can be applied as probiotics to recruit beneficial microbiomes (Figure 4A, B). In contrast, top-down approaches utilise existing microbiomes, either by direct transplantation or modifying them through selective passaging or virus-mediated engineering to enrich beneficial traits (Figure 4C-E). This section will discuss key findings in phyllosphere microbiome research on food crops under the framework of microbiome engineering.

Designer microbiomes as probiotics

A synthetic community (SynCom) is an assembly of functionally characterised microorganisms (Vorholt et al., 2017). It is commonly used as a simplified model of a complex microbial community to investigate factors that influence the microbiome assembly (Niu et al., 2017). Beyond fundamental studies, SynComs can be assembled from beneficial microorganisms to produce probiotics that enhance plant health by promoting growth and providing protection against diseases (Vassileva et al., 2020).

Combining several strains in a SynCom produces an additive effect that enhances the beneficial traits of individual strains. For example, different combinations of *Pseudomonas* strains, isolated from potatoes infected with the late blight oomycetes *Phytophthora infestans*, were tested using a leaf disk assay (De Vrieze et al., 2018). This identified combinations of two strains that exhibited higher protection against *P. infestans* than when applied individually (De Vrieze et al., 2018). Likewise, in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, bacterial strains that suppress *Pseudomonas syringae*

pv. tomato DC3000 were isolated and characterised (Vogel et al., 2021). A SynCom assembled using these strains showed enhanced disease suppression than when applying individual strains (Vogel et al., 2021). However, ensuring compatibility between different strains is a challenge when designing SynComs. A *Pseudomonas* strain with strong antagonistic activity against *P. infestans* was not effective in a SynCom, possibly due to competition with other strains that suppressed its growth in the community (De Vrieze et al., 2018). Further studies on individual microbe-microbe interactions are needed to build effective microbial communities.

Furthermore, a SynCom consisting of dominant leaf bacteria from field-grown tomatoes was sprayed onto tomatoes in the greenhouse (Mehlferber et al., 2023). This led to significant increase in fruit production and improved the nutritional state of the plant, which enabled disease protection against *Pseudomonas syringae*. However, this enhanced growth effect was not observed in the field trial, possibly due to variations in the host genotypes and exposure to environmental perturbations which led to the decline of the SynCom. Nevertheless, these findings suggest the potential use of field-derived microbiome as biostimulants for greenhouse plants as they have a lower microbiome diversity than field-grown plants due to the limited interactions with the surrounding environment (Mehlferber et al., 2023).

A major bottleneck of SynCom is the need to isolate and culture microorganisms. It is estimated that only 1% of bacteria can be cultured on synthetic media, restricting the diversity of SynComs that could be designed (Staley and Konopka, 1985; Vartoukian, Palmer and Wade, 2010). To date, a cultured collection of phyllosphere microbiome has only been established in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Bai et al., 2015). Therefore, assembling SynComs for agriculturally relevant crops would require the development of high-throughput methods to culture and characterise a wide range of strains, which poses a major challenge (Vorholt et al., 2017). In addition, further studies are needed to test the persistence of SynComs under environmental conditions.

Recruiting beneficial microbiomes using prebiotics

Prebiotics are substances such as metabolites and polysaccharides that provide health benefit to the plant by stimulating the growth or beneficial activity of targeted microorganisms (Gibson and Roberfroid, 1995; Markowiak and Śliżewska, 2017). They are commonly consumed as supplements to enhance the gut microbiome in humans (Sanders et al., 2019). This concept could be applied to plants as several studies have identified key metabolites in the phyllosphere that are involved in recruiting selective microorganisms with beneficial traits. For example, a

metabolic profiling revealed production of L-ornithine in rice leaves infected by *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Jiang et al., 2025). Further assays showed that L-ornithine was involved in recruiting and enhancing the growth of the three core bacterial taxa, *Brevundimonas*, *Pantoea* and *Stenotrophomonas*. These bacteria reduced disease symptoms through production of antimicrobial compounds or by activating hormone-dependent defence mechanisms and upregulating defence enzymes in plants (Jiang et al., 2025).

Similarly, application of salt-tolerant *Bacillus* strain RA on tomatoes under stress condition led to an increase in the production of *myo*-inositol (Wu et al., 2024). The exogenous application of *myo*-inositol on tomatoes enhanced their phyllosphere bacterial diversity, complexity and connectivity which is associated with higher robustness and resilience of microbial communities under environmental perturbations (Wu et al., 2024). Taken together, these findings provide candidate metabolites that could be developed into prebiotics. Integration of metabolomics when characterising phyllosphere microbiomes could lead to discovery of new metabolic markers for prebiotics (Wu et al., 2024).

Microbiome transplant

Transplant of the entire microbiome is an example of a top-down microbiome engineering approach that directly uses an existing microbiome. In medical research, faecal transplantation, which involves transfer of gut microbiome from a healthy donor to a patient, was demonstrated as a successful treatment for chronic gastrointestinal disorders (Wang et al., 2019). A similar approach was used in coffee, where the transfer of microbiota from rust-resistant lines to susceptible lines, resulting in reduced rust symptoms of rust caused by *Hemileia vastatrix* in an in vitro leaf disc experiment (de Sousa and Mondego, 2024).

Likewise, the occurrence of cotton leaf curl disease was reduced in susceptible cotton lines after transplanting bacteria from disease-resistant lines in a net house experiment (Badar et al., 2025). Functional profiling based on amplicon data suggested that the phyllosphere bacteria on resistant lines exhibited upregulation of starch biosynthesis, amino sugar metabolism, phospholipase synthesis and degradation of Vitamin B6 and taurine, which provided nutrients for to support the growth of other bacteria. This contributed to the improved resilience of cotton against the disease (Badar et al., 2025).

Furthermore, co-transplantation of phyllosphere and rhizosphere microbiome from field-grown sugarcane increased diversity, network connectivity and improved plant growth of sugarcane grown in controlled condition (Khoiri et al., 2024). However, phyllosphere transplants were less effective compared to rhizosphere transplants, likely due to the lower nutrient availability in the phyllosphere compared to soil, limiting the viability of transferred microbiome in the new habitat (Khoiri et al., 2024; Vorholt, 2012).

Microbiome transplants maintains the functional complexity of the donor microbial community, enabling more stable establishment in the host compared to application of individual strains or SynComs which are often outcompeted by the recipient's microbiota (Badar et al., 2025). However, phyllosphere microbiome transplant has only been tested under controlled conditions and its effectiveness in the field under the influence of environmental factors remain unclear. Scaling up this method also poses challenges, as it would require production of large quantities of donor microbiomes using culture-independent techniques which has not yet been explored.

Using artificial selection to develop resilient microbiomes

Artificial interventions can enhance the desired traits of existing microbiomes before transferring them to a recipient. One approach is successive passaging where microbial community is repeatedly inoculated onto new hosts with along with a selective pressure, such as pathogens (Morella et al., 2020). Prolonged exposure to these stress conditions refines desirable traits, such as disease resistance, within the microbiome over time (Morella et al., 2020).

This was demonstrated on tomatoes where microbiota sampled from field-grown plants were passaged over nine cycles on greenhouse-grown tomatoes to develop resilience against the bacterial pathogen, *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* (Ehau-Taumaunu and Hockett, 2023). Subsequent inoculation of tomato plants with the passaged community showed significantly lower disease symptoms compared to the treatment with the non-passaged controls, suggesting the enrichment of disease-suppressing traits. Likewise, a microbial community with disease-suppressive traits against the wheat head blight fungus, *Fusarium graminearum*, was obtained through several cycles of applying field-isolated bacteria and the pathogen onto detached wheat ears (Deroo et al., 2022). Further assays identified bacterial species that inhibited *F. graminearum* growth and reduced mycotoxin production, thereby contributing to reduced disease severity in a cross-kingdom manner (Deroo et al., 2022).

Taken together, these studies demonstrate the potential use of culture-independent, *in planta* methods to evolve microbial communities with desirable traits. Greenhouse and field trials are required to assess the disease-suppressing capacity under various environmental conditions. Additionally, comparing the originally isolated microbiome extract with the passaged microbiota could reveal molecular and metabolic changes that enhance disease suppression, providing valuable insights to optimise microbiome engineering.

Viruses as tools for microbiome engineering

Bacteriophage viruses (Phages) are abundant viruses that target bacteria (Jiang et al., 2023). Lytic phages can hijack the host's machinery for replication and kill the host to release the viral progeny (Batinovic et al., 2019). Host-specific phages can be used to target particular bacterial strains, making them promising biocontrol agents and valuable tools for precise engineering of microbiomes (Fujiwara et al., 2011; Tanaka et al., 2024).

Phages can significantly alter the phyllosphere bacterial community (Morella et al., 2018). In this study, field-derived microbial extract was sprayed onto greenhouse-grown tomatoes, either directly or after the removal of phages. Plants treated with complete extracts showed a reduction in bacterial abundance but higher diversity compared to those treated with phage-free extracts (Morella et al., 2018). This could be due to the lysis of dominant bacterial taxa targeted by the phages, which led to increased resource availability, promoting the growth of non-dominant bacteria (Morella et al., 2018). Furthermore, phage treatment targeting the rice leaf blight bacteria *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* resulted in a reduction of disease symptoms by decreasing the abundance of the pathogenic bacteria (Jiang et al., 2023). Additionally, an increase of bacterial diversity was also observed, indicating higher microbiome stability (Jiang et al., 2023). Although the effects of phages have only been tested under controlled conditions, they highlight the potential use of phages in phyllosphere microbiome engineering.

Furthermore, phage genomes can be modified using Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) to alter their host range, modulate lytic activity and potentially deactivate virulence genes in pathogens (Mahler et al., 2023). These methods could be used for targeted removal of selected bacterial taxa to modulate microbiome functions (Mahler et al., 2023).

Virus-mediated engineering could be extended to fungi using mycoviruses which target fungi (Hough et al., 2023). Some mycoviruses exhibit hypovirulence where the virus reduces the growth and pathogenicity of their host, indicating their use as potential biocontrol agents (Nuss, 1992). One study identified novel mycoviruses from soybean leaves using transcriptomics (Marzano and Domier, 2016). Among them, a single-stranded DNA mycovirus with high similarity to SsHaDV-1 was found. SsHaDV-1 exhibits fungicidal activity against the common pathogenic fungus, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Yu et al., 2013). Further studies are needed to characterise the role of SsHaDV-1 in the phyllosphere. The use of transcriptomics can advance research on the diversity and function of viral agents and their target hosts, enabling potential applications of viruses in microbiome engineering (Liu et al., 2021).

M genes for microbiome-based breeding

An alternative strategy for modulating the phyllosphere microbiome is to target the host plant, as plant genetics strongly influence their morphological and metabolic traits, which indirectly shape the associated microbiomes (Kusstascher et al., 2020). However, studying the microbiome from a genetic perspective is relatively new.

The concept of microbiome-shaping genes (M genes) was introduced by Zhan and Wang (2024) which describe a set of genes that control plant microbiome assembly. M genes can be found using genome-wide association study (GWAS) in which a panel of diverse genotypes are screened to identify genetic markers associated with a specific phenotype (Beilsmith et al., 2019). An extensive GWAS was performed on 110 rice accessions which identified one gene, *OsPAL02* encoding an enzyme in the lignin biosynthesis pathway that convert L-tyrosine to 4-hydroxycinnamic acid (4-HCA) (Su et al., 2024). *OsPAL02* was strongly associated with the abundance of *Pseudomonadales*, one of the four dominant bacterial orders in the rice phyllosphere (Su et al., 2024). *OsPAL02* knockout caused dysbiosis which increased plant's susceptibility to the bacterial pathogen, *Xanthomonas oryzae*. This was restored by the exogenous application of 4-HCA, confirming the function of the gene in shaping the phyllosphere bacterial community (Su et al., 2024). The identified M genes could be used in novel microbiome-based breeding programs that select plants species with beneficial microbiomes.

Similarly, genes involved in plant immunity, cell wall structure and metabolism were among the M gene candidates identified through GWAS in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and citrus (Horton et al.,

2014; Xu et al., 2023). Furthermore, quantitative trait loci (QTL) mapping of a genetic cross between canker-resistant apple cultivars identified loci associated with bacterial and fungal endophyte abundance that may contribute to disease resistance (Karlström et al., 2023). However, these studies lack further experiments to characterise the candidate genes. In addition, genetic loci associated with microbiome assembly could not be identified in a GWAS of 300 maize lines and suggested that environmental factors likely played a more significant role in microbial assembly than genetic factors (Wallace et al., 2018). Although the findings of Su et al. (2024) demonstrate GWAS as a powerful tool to link microbiome phenotypes with plant genetics, this is yet to be reproduced in other crop species.

Other studies have identified distinct phyllosphere microbiomes between disease-resistant and susceptible plant genotypes which may be linked to underlying M genes. In maize, cultivars resistant to northern corn leaf blight harboured distinct bacterial taxa compared to susceptible cultivars (Xueliang et al., 2020). Further analysis showed that variations in leaf chemical traits could contribute to the differences in bacterial communities (Xueliang et al., 2020). Similarly, distinct bacterial communities were found on the mature leaves of grapevine cultivars with difference in disease resistance to downy mildew (Wicaksono et al., 2023). In situ hybridisation and observations on confocal microscopy revealed distinct spatial distribution of bacteria on the leaf and variations in leaf hair density between the two cultivars (Wicaksono et al., 2023). However, this study did not investigate if the disease resistance was driven by variations in leaf morphology which could have contributed to the composition of associated microorganisms. Genetic approaches, such as mutagenesis, along with spatial and metabolic profiling, are needed to disentangle the relationship between microbiome traits and host genetics.

Transforming agricultural practices

Anthropogenic factors such as synthetic chemicals and farming practices can significantly alter the indigenous phyllosphere microbiome. These findings can be used to modulate farming practices to support healthy microbiomes on crops. For example, fungicide application reduced the abundance and diversity of bacteria and fungi in the phyllosphere of soybean, maize, eggplant and strawberry, suggesting their indirect effect on non-targeted microbes (Hoda & Aggarwal, 2024; Wei et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020). Furthermore, wheat grown on organic farms had higher microbial richness compared to those grown on conventional fields (Karlsson et al., 2017). This was attributed to increased weed in the absence of herbicide use, which enriched the microbial diversity surrounding the crop (Karlsson et al., 2017). These observations suggest

that reduced use of pesticides and herbicides could help preserve beneficial microbial communities on crop surfaces.

Additionally, no-till farming systems demonstrated a higher recovery of fungal networks following fungicide application, with 61% of core microbiome recovered compared to 34% in conventional systems (Noel et al., 2022). This was likely due to aerial spore dispersal by yeasts persisting in residual crops from the previous season in no-till fields (Noel et al., 2022). Although the underlying molecular mechanisms remain unclear, these findings suggest that principles of regenerative agriculture, such as minimal chemical input and no-till management may support the resilience and health of the phyllosphere microbiome (Khangura et al., 2023).

While the use of livestock manure as fertilisers enhances microbiome richness in organic farming, it is also associated with increased abundance of phyllosphere bacteria carrying antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), raising concerns about the spread of antibiotic resistance (Chen et al., 2018, 2020). This was seen in lettuce and bok choy and the proposed mechanisms of ARG transmission to the leaf included soil-to-root and root-to-leaf transfer or aerial dispersal (Li et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2019). Biochar, or charcoal, could serve as an alternative to manure for enhancing microbiome richness without contributing to the spread of ARGs (Li et al., 2025).

Various strategies for manipulating the microbiome can be integrated into existing farming practices. This was demonstrated in a study that tested a combination of synthetic fertilisers and a SynCom, consisting of three yeast strains with growth-promoting traits isolated from rice (Muthukrishnan et al., 2024). Greenhouse and field trials showed that combining the SynCom with 75% of the recommended fertiliser dosage most effectively increased the growth and yield of rice compared to using fertilisers or SynComs alone. Such integrated research methods help identify ways to rapidly incorporate new findings into current farming practices. These can help reduce the use of chemicals while complementing current limitations of microbiome-based methods, promoting the transition towards sustainable agricultural practices.

Conclusion

Phyllosphere microbiome research is still its early stages with most studies focusing on characterising the composition and diversity of microbial communities with a bias towards bacteria and fungi. Combining sequencing with multi-omics approaches is key to address the current knowledge gaps in the genetic and molecular basis of microbiome traits, including enhanced plant health and resilience against disease. Recent advances in identifying plant genes linked to beneficial microbiomes present a promising strategy for incorporation into breeding programs compared to microbiome engineering approaches, which pose significant challenges in scalability. Further studies are required to validate these findings under field conditions. Moving forward, most widely studied crops, such as rice and tomatoes, could serve

as model systems for demonstrating proof-of-concept for microbiome-based strategies. Ultimately, integrated research methods that incorporate current findings into existing farming practices will be key to promote transition towards sustainable agriculture to meet the growing global food demand.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Professor Sebastian Eves-van den Akker for his guidance during the initial discussion. I would also like to express my gratitude to Dr Albin Teulet, Dr Darius Kosmützky and Dr Alex Guyon from the Schornack group for their valuable advice on the draft of this essay.

References

- Agler, M.T., Ruhe, J., Kroll, S., Morhenn, C., Kim, S.-T., Weigel, D. & Kemen, E.M. (2016) Microbial Hub Taxa Link Host and Abiotic Factors to Plant Microbiome Variation. *PLOS Biology*. 14 (1), e1002352. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002352.
- Aguiar-Pulido, V., Huang, W., Suarez-Ulloa, V., Cickovski, T., Mathee, K. & Narasimhan, G. (2016) Metagenomics, Metatranscriptomics, and Metabolomics Approaches for Microbiome Analysis: Supplementary Issue: Bioinformatics Methods and Applications for Big Metagenomics Data. *Evolutionary Bioinformatics*. 12s1, EBO.S36436. doi:10.4137/EBO.S36436.
- Awad, M., Giannopoulos, G., Mylona, P.V. & Polidoros, A.N. (2023) Comparative Analysis of Grapevine Epiphytic Microbiomes among Different Varieties, Tissues, and Developmental Stages in the Same Terroir. *Applied Sciences*. 13 (1), 102. doi:10.3390/app13010102.
- Badar, A., Aqueel, R., Nawaz, A., Ijaz, U.Z. & Malik, K.A. (2025) Microbiota transplantation for cotton leaf curl disease suppression—core microbiome and transcriptome dynamics. *Communications Biology*. 8 (1), 1–16. doi:10.1038/s42003-025-07812-7.
- Bai, Y., Müller, D.B., Srinivas, G., Garrido-Oter, R., Potthoff, E., Rott, M., Dombrowski, N., Münch, P.C., Spaepen, S., Remus-Emsermann, M., Hüttel, B., McHardy, A.C., Vorholt, J.A. & Schulze-Lefert, P. (2015) Functional overlap of the Arabidopsis leaf and root microbiota. *Nature*. 528 (7582), 364–369. doi:10.1038/nature16192.
- Bashir, I., War, A.F., Rafiq, I., Reshi, Z.A., Rashid, I. & Shouche, Y.S. (2022) Phyllosphere microbiome: Diversity and functions. *Microbiological Research*. 254, 126888. doi:10.1016/j.micres.2021.126888.
- Batinovic, S., Wassef, F., Knowler, S.A., Rice, D.T.F., Stanton, C.R., Rose, J., Tucci, J., Nittami, T., Vinh, A., Drummond, G.R., Sobey, C.G., Chan, H.T., Seviour, R.J., Petrovski, S. & Franks, A.E. (2019) Bacteriophages in Natural and Artificial Environments. *Pathogens*. 8 (3), 100. doi:10.3390/pathogens8030100.
- Beilsmith, K., Thoen, M.P.M., Brachi, B., Gloss, A.D., Khan, M.H. & Bergelson, J. (2019) Genome-wide association studies on the phyllosphere microbiome: Embracing complexity in host–microbe interactions. *The Plant Journal*. 97 (1), 164–181. doi:10.1111/tbj.14170.
- Berg, G., Rybakova, D., Fischer, D., Cernava, T., Vergès, M.-C.C., et al. (2020) Microbiome definition re-visited: old concepts and new challenges. *Microbiome*. 8 (1), 103. doi:10.1186/s40168-020-00875-0.
- Campbell, B., Beare, D., Bennett, E., Hall-Spencer, J., Ingram, J., Jaramillo, F., Ortiz, R., Ramankutty, N., Sayer, J. & Shindell, D. (2017) Agriculture production as a major driver of the Earth system exceeding planetary boundaries. *Ecology and Society*. 22 (4). doi:10.5751/ES-09595-220408.
- Chaudhry, V., Runge, P., Sengupta, P., Doehlemann, G., Parker, J.E. & Kemen, E. (2021) Shaping the leaf microbiota: plant–microbe–microbe interactions. *Journal of Experimental Botany*. 72 (1), 36–56. doi:10.1093/jxb/eraa417.

- Chen, Q.-L., An, X.-L., Zheng, B.-X., Ma, Y.-B. & Su, J.-Q. (2018) Long-term organic fertilization increased antibiotic resistome in phyllosphere of maize. *Science of The Total Environment*. 645, 1230–1237. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.07.260.
- Chen, Q.-L., Hu, H.-W., Zhu, D., Ding, J., Yan, Z.-Z., He, J.-Z. & Zhu, Y.-G. (2020) Host identity determines plant associated resistomes. *Environmental Pollution*. 258, 113709. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113709.
- De Mandal, S. & Jeon, J. (2023) Phyllosphere Microbiome in Plant Health and Disease. *Plants*. 12 (19), 3481. doi:10.3390/plants12193481.
- De Vrieze, M., Germanier, F., Vuille, N. & Weisskopf, L. (2018) Combining Different Potato-Associated *Pseudomonas* Strains for Improved Biocontrol of *Phytophthora infestans*. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 9. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.02573.
- Deroo, W., De Troyer, L., Dumoulin, F., De Saeger, S., De Boevre, M., Vandenabeele, S., De Gelder, L. & Audenaert, K. (2022) A Novel In Planta Enrichment Method Employing *Fusarium graminearum*-Infected Wheat Spikes to Select for Competitive Biocontrol Bacteria. *Toxins*. 14 (3), 222. doi:10.3390/toxins14030222.
- de Sousa, L.P. & Mondego, J.M.C. (2024) Leaf surface microbiota transplantation confers resistance to coffee leaf rust in susceptible *Coffea arabica*. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*. 100 (6), fiae049. doi:10.1093/femsec/fiae049.
- van Dijk, M., Morley, T., Rau, M.L. & Saghai, Y. (2021) A meta-analysis of projected global food demand and population at risk of hunger for the period 2010–2050. *Nature Food*. 2 (7), 494–501. doi:10.1038/s43016-021-00322-9.
- Ehau-Taumaunu, H. & Hockett, K.L. (2023) Passaging Phyllosphere Microbial Communities Develop Suppression Towards Bacterial Speck Disease in Tomato. *Phytobiomes Journal*. 7 (2), 233–243. doi:10.1094/PBIOMES-05-22-0030-FI.
- Faust, K. & Raes, J. (2012) Microbial interactions: from networks to models. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*. 10 (8), 538–550. doi:10.1038/nrmicro2832.
- Fujiwara, A., Fujisawa, M., Hamasaki, R., Kawasaki, T., Fujie, M. & Yamada, T. (2011) Biocontrol of *Ralstonia solanacearum* by Treatment with Lytic Bacteriophages. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 77 (12), 4155–4162. doi:10.1128/AEM.02847-10.
- Garnett, T., Appleby, M.C., Balmford, A., Bateman, I.J., Benton, T.G., Bloomer, P., Burlingame, B., Dawkins, M., Dolan, L., Fraser, D., Herrero, M., Hoffmann, I., Smith, P., Thornton, P.K., Toulmin, C., Vermeulen, S.J. & Godfray, H.C.J. (2013) Sustainable Intensification in Agriculture: Premises and Policies. *Science*. 341 (6141), 33–34. doi:10.1126/science.1234485.
- Gibson, G.R. & Roberfroid, M.B. (1995) Dietary Modulation of the Human Colonic Microbiota: Introducing the Concept of Prebiotics. *The Journal of Nutrition*. 125 (6), 1401–1412. doi:10.1093/jn/125.6.1401.
- Handelsman, J., Rondon, M.R., Brady, S.F., Clardy, J. & Goodman, R.M. (1998) Molecular biological access to the chemistry of unknown soil microbes: a new frontier for natural products. *Chemistry & Biology*. 5 (10), R245–R249. doi:10.1016/S1074-5521(98)90108-9.

- Hoda, S. & Aggarwal, K.K. (2024) Impact of Organophosphates on Diversity and Functional Characteristics of Phyllosphere Bacterial Communities of *Solanum melongena*. *Indian Journal of Microbiology*. doi:10.1007/s12088-024-01322-6.
- Horton, M.W., Bodenhausen, N., Beilsmith, K., Meng, D., Muegge, B.D., Subramanian, S., Vetter, M.M., Vilhjálmsson, B.J., Nordborg, M., Gordon, J.I. & Bergelson, J. (2014) Genome-wide association study of *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf microbial community. *Nature Communications*. 5 (1), 5320. doi:10.1038/ncomms6320.
- Hu, H.-W., Chen, Q.-L. & He, J.-Z. (2022) The end of hunger: fertilizers, microbes and plant productivity. *Microbial Biotechnology*. 15 (4), 1050–1054. doi:10.1111/1751-7915.13973.
- Jiang, H., Li, C., Huang, X., Ahmed, T., Ogunyemi, S.O., Yu, S., Wang, X., Ali, H.M., Khan, F., Yan, C., Chen, J. & Li, B. (2023) Phage combination alleviates bacterial leaf blight of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 14. doi:10.3389/fpls.2023.1147351.
- Jiang, H., Xu, X., Lv, L., Huang, X., Ahmed, T., Tian, Y., Hu, S., Chen, J. & Li, B. (2025) Host Metabolic Alterations Mediate Phyllosphere Microbes Defense upon *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv *oryzae* Infection. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 73 (1), 249–259. doi:10.1021/acs.jafc.4c09178.
- Karlsson, I., Friberg, H., Kolseth, A.-K., Steinberg, C. & Persson, P. (2017) Organic farming increases richness of fungal taxa in the wheat phyllosphere. *Molecular Ecology*. 26 (13), 3424–3436. doi:10.1111/mec.14132.
- Karlström, A., Papp-Rupar, M., Passey, T.A.J., Deakin, G. & Xu, X. (2023) Quantitative trait loci associated with apple endophytes during pathogen infection. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 14. doi:10.3389/fpls.2023.1054914.
- Ke, J., Wang, B. & Yoshikuni, Y. (2021) Microbiome Engineering: Synthetic Biology of Plant-Associated Microbiomes in Sustainable Agriculture. *Trends in Biotechnology*. 39 (3), 244–261. doi:10.1016/j.tibtech.2020.07.008.
- Khangura, R., Ferris, D., Wagg, C. & Bowyer, J. (2023) Regenerative Agriculture—A Literature Review on the Practices and Mechanisms Used to Improve Soil Health. *Sustainability*. 15 (3), 2338. doi:10.3390/su15032338.
- Khoiri, A.N., Wattanachaisaereekul, S., Jirakkakul, J., Sutheeworapong, S., Kusonmano, K., Cheevadhanarak, S. & Prommeenate, P. (2024) Co-transplantation of phyllosphere and rhizosphere microbes promotes microbial colonization and enhances sugarcane growth. *Applied Soil Ecology*. 201, 105469. doi:10.1016/j.apsoil.2024.105469.
- Kusstatscher, P., Wicaksono, W.A., Bergna, A., Cernava, T., Bergau, N., Tissier, A., Hause, B. & Berg, G. (2020) Trichomes form genotype-specific microbial hotspots in the phyllosphere of tomato. *Environmental Microbiome*. 15 (1), 17. doi:10.1186/s40793-020-00364-9.
- Lawson, C.E., Harcombe, W.R., Hatzenpichler, R., Lindemann, S.R., Löffler, F.E., O'Malley, M.A., García Martín, H., Pflieger, B.F., Raskin, L., Venturelli, O.S., Weissbrodt, D.G., Noguera, D.R. & McMahon, K.D. (2019) Common principles and best practices for engineering microbiomes. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*. 17 (12), 725–741. doi:10.1038/s41579-019-0255-9.

- Li, K., Rahman, S. ur, Rehman, A., Li, H., Hui, N. & Khalid, M. (2025) Shaping rhizocompartments and phyllosphere microbiomes and antibiotic resistance genes: The influence of different fertilizer regimes and biochar application. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 487, 137148. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137148.
- Lindow, S.E. & Brandl, M.T. (2003) Microbiology of the Phyllosphere. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 69 (4), 1875–1883. doi:10.1128/AEM.69.4.1875-1883.2003.
- Liu, Y.-X., Qin, Y., Chen, T., Lu, M., Qian, X., Guo, X. & Bai, Y. (2021) A practical guide to amplicon and metagenomic analysis of microbiome data. *Protein & Cell*. 12 (5), 315–330. doi:10.1007/s13238-020-00724-8.
- Mahler, M., Costa, A.R., Beljouw, S.P.B. van, Fineran, P.C. & Brouns, S.J.J. (2023) Approaches for bacteriophage genome engineering. *Trends in Biotechnology*. 41 (5), 669–685. doi:10.1016/j.tibtech.2022.08.008.
- Marchesi, J.R. & Ravel, J. (2015) The vocabulary of microbiome research: a proposal. *Microbiome*. 3 (1), 31. doi:10.1186/s40168-015-0094-5.
- Markowiak, P. & Śliżewska, K. (2017) Effects of Probiotics, Prebiotics, and Synbiotics on Human Health. *Nutrients*. 9 (9), 1021. doi:10.3390/nu9091021.
- Marzano, S.-Y.L. & Domier, L.L. (2016) Novel mycoviruses discovered from metatranscriptomics survey of soybean phyllosphere phytobiomes. *Virus Research*. 213, 332–342. doi:10.1016/j.virusres.2015.11.002.
- Masuda, S., Gan, P., Kiguchi, Y., Anda, M., Sasaki, K., Shibata, A., Iwasaki, W., Suda, W. & Shirasu, K. (2024) Uncovering microbiomes of the rice phyllosphere using long-read metagenomic sequencing. *Communications Biology*. 7 (1), 1–13. doi:10.1038/s42003-024-05998-w.
- Mehlferber, E.C., Debray, R., Conover, A.E., Sherman, J.K., Kaulbach, G., Reed, R., McCue, K.F., Ferrel, J.E., Khanna, R. & Koskella, B. (2023) Phyllosphere microbial associations improve plant reproductive success. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 14. doi:10.3389/fpls.2023.1273330.
- Michl, K., Berg, G. & Cernava, T. (2023) The microbiome of cereal plants: The current state of knowledge and the potential for future applications. *Environmental Microbiome*. 18 (1), 28. doi:10.1186/s40793-023-00484-y.
- Morella, N.M., Gomez, A.L., Wang, G., Leung, M.S. & Koskella, B. (2018) The impact of bacteriophages on phyllosphere bacterial abundance and composition. *Molecular Ecology*. 27 (8), 2025–2038. doi:10.1111/mec.14542.
- Morella, N.M., Weng, F.C.-H., Joubert, P.M., Metcalf, C.J.E., Lindow, S. & Koskella, B. (2020) Successive passaging of a plant-associated microbiome reveals robust habitat and host genotype-dependent selection. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 117 (2), 1148–1159. doi:10.1073/pnas.1908600116.
- Muthukrishnan, G., Munisamy, J., Gopalasubramaniam, S.K., Subramanian, K.S., Dharmaraj, R., Nath, D.J., Dutta, P. & Devarajan, A.K. (2024) Impact of foliar application of phyllosphere

yeast strains combined with soil fertilizer application on rice growth and yield. *Environmental Microbiome*. 19 (1), 102. doi:10.1186/s40793-024-00635-9.

Niu, B., Paulson, J.N., Zheng, X. & Kolter, R. (2017) Simplified and representative bacterial community of maize roots. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 114 (12), E2450–E2459. doi:10.1073/pnas.1616148114.

Noel, Z.A., Longley, R., Benucci, G.M.N., Trail, F., Chilvers, M.I. & Bonito, G. (2022) Non-target impacts of fungicide disturbance on phyllosphere yeasts in conventional and no-till management. *ISME Communications*. 2 (1), 19. doi:10.1038/s43705-022-00103-w.

Nuss, D.L. (1992) Biological control of chestnut blight: an example of virus-mediated attenuation of fungal pathogenesis. *Microbiological Reviews*. 56 (4), 561–576. doi:10.1128/mr.56.4.561-576.1992.

Portik, D.M., Brown, C.T. & Pierce-Ward, N.T. (2022) Evaluation of taxonomic classification and profiling methods for long-read shotgun metagenomic sequencing datasets. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 23 (1), 541. doi:10.1186/s12859-022-05103-0.

Quince, C., Walker, A.W., Simpson, J.T., Loman, N.J. & Segata, N. (2017) Shotgun metagenomics, from sampling to analysis. *Nature Biotechnology*. 35 (9), 833–844. doi:10.1038/nbt.3935.

Regalado, J., Lundberg, D.S., Deusch, O., Kersten, S., Karasov, T., Poersch, K., Shirsekar, G. & Weigel, D. (2020) Combining whole-genome shotgun sequencing and rRNA gene amplicon analyses to improve detection of microbe–microbe interaction networks in plant leaves. *The ISME Journal*. 14 (8), 2116–2130. doi:10.1038/s41396-020-0665-8.

Remus-Emsermann, M.N.P., Lückner, S., Müller, D.B., Potthoff, E., Daims, H. & Vorholt, J.A. (2014) Spatial distribution analyses of natural phyllosphere-colonizing bacteria on *Arabidopsis thaliana* revealed by fluorescence in situ hybridization. *Environmental Microbiology*. 16 (7), 2329–2340. doi:10.1111/1462-2920.12482.

Remus-Emsermann, M.N.P. & Schlechter, R.O. (2018) Phyllosphere microbiology: at the interface between microbial individuals and the plant host. *New Phytologist*. 218 (4), 1327–1333. doi:10.1111/nph.15054.

Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S.E., et al. (2023) Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*. 9 (37), eadh2458. doi:10.1126/sciadv.adh2458.

Saarenpää, S., Shalev, O., Ashkenazy, H., Carlos, V., Lundberg, D.S., Weigel, D. & Giacomello, S. (2024) Spatial metatranscriptomics resolves host–bacteria–fungi interactomes. *Nature Biotechnology*. 42 (9), 1384–1393. doi:10.1038/s41587-023-01979-2.

Sanders, M.E., Merenstein, D.J., Reid, G., Gibson, G.R. & Rastall, R.A. (2019) Probiotics and prebiotics in intestinal health and disease: from biology to the clinic. *Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. 16 (10), 605–616. doi:10.1038/s41575-019-0173-3.

- Sapkota, R., Jørgensen, L.N. & Nicolaisen, M. (2017) Spatiotemporal Variation and Networks in the Mycobiome of the Wheat Canopy. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 8. doi:10.3389/fpls.2017.01357.
- Schoch, C.L., Seifert, K.A., Huhndorf, S., Robert, V., Spouge, J.L., et al. (2012) Nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region as a universal DNA barcode marker for Fungi. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 109 (16), 6241–6246. doi:10.1073/pnas.1117018109.
- Shade, A. & Handelsman, J. (2012) Beyond the Venn diagram: the hunt for a core microbiome. *Environmental Microbiology*. 14 (1), 4–12. doi:10.1111/j.1462-2920.2011.02585.x.
- Sohrabi, R., Paasch, B.C., Liber, J.A. & He, S.Y. (2023) Phyllosphere Microbiome. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*. 74 (Volume 74, 2023), 539–568. doi:10.1146/annurev-arplant-102820-032704.
- Staley, J.T. & Konopka, A. (1985) Measurement of in situ activities of nonphotosynthetic microorganisms in aquatic and terrestrial habitats. *Annual Review of Microbiology*. 39 (Volume 39,), 321–346. doi:10.1146/annurev.mi.39.100185.001541.
- Su, P., Kang, H., Peng, Q., Wicaksono, W.A., Berg, G., Liu, Z., Ma, J., Zhang, D., Cernava, T. & Liu, Y. (2024) Microbiome homeostasis on rice leaves is regulated by a precursor molecule of lignin biosynthesis. *Nature Communications*. 15 (1), 23. doi:10.1038/s41467-023-44335-3.
- Su, P., Wicaksono, W.A., Li, C., Michl, K., Berg, G., Wang, D., Xiao, Y., Huang, R., Kang, H., Zhang, D., Cernava, T. & Liu, Y. (2022) Recovery of metagenome-assembled genomes from the phyllosphere of 110 rice genotypes. *Scientific Data*. 9 (1), 254. doi:10.1038/s41597-022-01320-7.
- Sun, A., Jiao, X.-Y., Chen, Q., Trivedi, P., Li, Z., Li, F., Zheng, Y., Lin, Y., Hu, H.-W. & He, J.-Z. (2021) Fertilization alters protistan consumers and parasites in crop-associated microbiomes. *Environmental Microbiology*. 23 (4), 2169–2183. doi:10.1111/1462-2920.15385.
- Taffner, J., Cernava, T., Erlacher, A. & Berg, G. (2019) Novel insights into plant-associated archaea and their functioning in arugula (*Eruca sativa* Mill.). *Journal of Advanced Research*. 19, 39–48. doi:10.1016/j.jare.2019.04.008.
- Tanaka, T., Sugiyama, R., Sato, Y., Kawaguchi, M., Honda, K., Iwaki, H. & Okano, K. (2024) Precise microbiome engineering using natural and synthetic bacteriophages targeting an artificial bacterial consortium. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 15. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2024.1403903.
- Toju, H., Peay, K.G., Yamamichi, M., Narisawa, K., Hiruma, K., Naito, K., Fukuda, S., Ushio, M., Nakaoka, S., Onoda, Y., Yoshida, K., Schlaeppi, K., Bai, Y., Sugiura, R., Ichihashi, Y., Minamisawa, K. & Kiers, E.T. (2018) Core microbiomes for sustainable agroecosystems. *Nature Plants*. 4 (5), 247–257. doi:10.1038/s41477-018-0139-4.
- UN (2017) *World population projected to reach 9.8 billion in 2050, and 11.2 billion in 2100*. 2017. United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/desa/world-population-projected-reach-98-billion-2050-and-112-billion-2100> [Accessed: 12 March 2025].

- Vartoukian, S.R., Palmer, R.M. & Wade, W.G. (2010) Strategies for culture of 'unculturable' bacteria. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*. 309 (1), 1–7. doi:10.1111/j.1574-6968.2010.02000.x.
- Vassileva, M., Flor-Peregrin, E., Malusá, E. & Vassilev, N. (2020) Towards Better Understanding of the Interactions and Efficient Application of Plant Beneficial Prebiotics, Probiotics, Postbiotics and Synbiotics. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 11. doi:10.3389/fpls.2020.01068.
- Vogel, C.M., Potthoff, D.B., Schäfer, M., Barandun, N. & Vorholt, J.A. (2021) Protective role of the *Arabidopsis* leaf microbiota against a bacterial pathogen. *Nature Microbiology*. 6 (12), 1537–1548. doi:10.1038/s41564-021-00997-7.
- Vorholt, J.A. (2012) Microbial life in the phyllosphere. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*. 10 (12), 828–840. doi:10.1038/nrmicro2910.
- Vorholt, J.A., Vogel, C., Carlström, C.I. & Müller, D.B. (2017) Establishing Causality: Opportunities of Synthetic Communities for Plant Microbiome Research. *Cell Host & Microbe*. 22 (2), 142–155. doi:10.1016/j.chom.2017.07.004.
- Wallace, J.G., Kremling, K.A., Kovar, L.L. & Buckler, E.S. (2018) Quantitative Genetics of the Maize Leaf Microbiome. *Phytobiomes Journal*. 2 (4), 208–224. doi:10.1094/PBIOMES-02-18-0008-R.
- Wang, J.-W., Kuo, C.-H., Kuo, F.-C., Wang, Y.-K., Hsu, W.-H., Yu, F.-J., Hu, H.-M., Hsu, P.-I., Wang, J.-Y. & Wu, D.-C. (2019) Fecal microbiota transplantation: Review and update. *Journal of the Formosan Medical Association*. 118, S23–S31. doi:10.1016/j.jfma.2018.08.011.
- Wei, N., Russell, A.L., Jarrett, A.R. & Ashman, T.-L. (2021) Pollinators mediate floral microbial diversity and microbial network under agrochemical disturbance. *Molecular Ecology*. 30 (10), 2235–2247. doi:10.1111/mec.15890.
- Wicaksono, W.A., Morauf, C., Müller, H., Abdelfattah, A., Donat, C. & Berg, G. (2023) The mature phyllosphere microbiome of grapevine is associated with resistance against *Plasmopara viticola*. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 14. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2023.1149307.
- Wu, F., Chen, Z., Xu, X., Xue, X., Zhang, Y. & Sui, N. (2024) Halotolerant *Bacillus* sp. strain RA coordinates myo-inositol metabolism to confer salt tolerance to tomato. *Journal of Integrative Plant Biology*. 66 (9), 1871–1885. doi:10.1111/jipb.13733.
- Xu, J., Wang, Y., Zhang, Y., Riera, N., Li, J., Clark, K.J., Jin, T., Chen, H., Wen, J., Ma, W., Liu, H. & Wang, N. (2023) Host Genetic Traits Underlying the Composition and Assembly of the Citrus Microbiome. *Phytobiomes Journal*. 7 (3), 401–411. doi:10.1094/PBIOMES-09-22-0059-R.
- Xu, N., Qu, Q., Zhang, Z., Yuan, W., Cui, H., Shen, Y., Lin, W., Lu, T. & Qian, H. (2020) Effects of residual S-metolachlor in soil on the phyllosphere microbial communities of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Science of The Total Environment*. 748, 141342. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141342.
- Xueliang, T., Dan, X., Tingting, S., Songyu, Z., Ying, L. & Diandong, W. (2020) Plant resistance and leaf chemical characteristic jointly shape phyllosphere bacterial community. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*. 36 (9), 139. doi:10.1007/s11274-020-02908-0.

Yu, X., Li, B., Fu, Y., Xie, J., Cheng, J., Ghabrial, S.A., Li, G., Yi, X. & Jiang, D. (2013) Extracellular transmission of a DNA mycovirus and its use as a natural fungicide. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 110 (4), 1452–1457. doi:10.1073/pnas.1213755110.

Zhan, C. & Wang, M. (2024) Disease resistance through M genes. *Nature Plants*. 10 (3), 352–353. doi:10.1038/s41477-024-01644-9.

Zhang, Y.-J., Hu, H.-W., Chen, Q.-L., Singh, B.K., Yan, H., Chen, D. & He, J.-Z. (2019) Transfer of antibiotic resistance from manure-amended soils to vegetable microbiomes. *Environment International*. 130, 104912. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2019.104912.

Zilber-Rosenberg, I. & Rosenberg, E. (2008) Role of microorganisms in the evolution of animals and plants: the hologenome theory of evolution. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*. 32 (5), 723–735. doi:10.1111/j.1574-6976.2008.00123.x.